

2A: COA Comparison and Evaluation Tool for Julia

Trial	Condition ——	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Condition ——	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Constant Variables	Test Variables	Outcome	Conclusions Next Steps
1	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Repeat
2	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Repeat
3	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Escape seems valuable, Evaluate attention and escape
4	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Repeat
5	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Repeat
6	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Escape seems to be a reinforcer, Evaluate social positives to determine the role of attention and tangible
7	C	Academic Demands, Attention	D	Escape, Tangible		Escape, Tangible	Escape, Tangible	Repeat
8	C	Academic Demands, Attention	D	Escape, Tangible		Escape, Tangible	Escape, Tangible	Repeat
9	C	Academic Demands, Attention	D	Escape, Tangible		Escape, Tangible	Escape, Tangible	Compare tangible with tangible and attention
10	D	Tangible	E	Tangible, Attention	Tangible	Attention	Tangible, Attention	Repeat

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11	D	Tangible	E	Tangible, Attention	Tangible	Attention	Tangible, Attention	Repeat
12	D	Tangible	E	Tangible, Attention	Tangible	Attention	Tangible, Attention	Compare tangible and attention
13	E	Tangible, Attention	F	Attention	Attention	Tangible	Tangible, Attention	Repeat
14	E	Tangible, Attention	F	Attention	Attention	Tangible	Tangible, Attention	Repeat
15	E	Tangible, Attention	F	Attention	Attention	Tangible	Tangible, Attention	When given the option, Julia allocates toward both attention and tangible which could be used to treat escape, Evaluate the role of high and low-preferred tangible items for treatment
16	D	Tangible	G	Low-preferred Tangible	Tangible	High-preferred vs. Low-preferred Tangibles	Tangible	Switching back and forth, Repeat
17	D	Tangible	G	Low-preferred Tangible	Tangible	High-preferred vs. Low-preferred Tangibles	Tangible	Switching back and forth, Repeat
18	D	Tangible	G	Low-preferred Tangible	Tangible	High-preferred vs. Low-preferred Tangibles	Tangible	Switching back and forth, Repeat
19	D	Tangible	G	Low-preferred Tangible	Tangible	High-preferred vs. Low-preferred Tangibles	Equal allocation	Switching back and forth, Repeat

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20	D	Tangible	G	Low-preferred Tangible	Tangible	High-preferred vs. Low-preferred Tangibles	Tangible	No clear preference for tangible type, Incorporate all tangibles into intervention
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